

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG PEOPLE AT HOME

Toshpo'latova Maxbuba Ikromovna

The Fergana Branch of Tashkent University of
Information Technology,
Senior Teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10008186>

Abstract: This article talks about the methods of teaching English to young children through easy, understandable and convenient methods at home. It is not about memorizing grammar rules for the development of speech, but what they have learned, heard, seen to form their speech, or can cause it to arise by itself.

Keywords: association, homework, repetition, parents, mechanic.

Nowadays, learning English is not for self-development, but for necessity. Foreign languages are taught not only in universities and schools, but also in pre-school educational institutions. But not all children can go to preschools. It should be noted that now knowing the language helps you find your place in society faster. Parents who did not feel the need to teach a language to a young child are now regretting it. Therefore, teaching from a young age is an achievement. Language learning depends on age and periods. Psychologists say that compared to adults, children have a stronger ability to learn languages. They have the ability to quickly perform and understand the task assigned to them. It should be noted that children of kindergarten age do not understand something, but memorize it mechanically. Many parents want their children to learn English from a young age. It is true that the age of language learning is not limited, but the best period is to start from 4-5 years old. Even now, when we are learning English, we memorize various grammar rules one by one. This is difficult and difficult. Pre-school age is a very convenient time to start learning a foreign language, that is, learning English. Because children of this age are very diligent, eager for knowledge, interested in learning everything around them. They immediately learn the rules that they have memorized carefully. It is not necessary to force them, because it can kill their interest in learning the language. When a child does not want to learn, when you start with difficult topics that he does not understand, when you do not know what to teach, or any number of similar reasons..

The main goals of teaching preschool children a foreign language:

- formation of children's ability to communicate;

- climb one step higher to achieve one's goals;
- learning to express one's opinion freely and completely to the people around;
- arouse interest in culture, history, lifestyle of other countries;
- not to be distracted by useless things;
- to save time and teach to spend it carefully.

Although it has not yet been proven how a child can learn a language in a short time, it is the same. A child has the ability to learn 2-3 different languages at the same time. The main thing is to deal with it. It is not surprising that this article is a textbook for parents who want to teach their child English, but do not know where to start. You don't need to have an excellent level of English to teach your child English. The main thing is that you can encourage and support your child. Of course, your child will not speak fluently very quickly. But don't stop trying, be patient.

There are several methods of teaching English at home. This article presents the most effective of them.

First of all, we must introduce the child to the English alphabet. True, it takes a lot of time (about 1-2 hours a day). But in order to learn everything faster, the child should be familiar with the alphabet. For this, you should set aside a special time for your child every day for the alphabet. How do you teach this? You start teaching by first writing the uppercase letter and then lowercase letters in the notebook. You spend at least 2 days per letter (one day for writing, one day for pronunciation). This means that your child will finish the alphabet in about 2 months. In addition, it should be noted that singing a song is more effective than simply memorizing the alphabet.

Growing your child's vocabulary is the second most important issue of language teaching. Divide the words you are teaching your child into two. Regular, that is, daily active words and reserve, that is, words that are not used much.

An effective method of storing and using words in memory quickly and reliably is memorization by association.

In order to teach English at home, association helps us, first of all, to connect with objects that are quickly and easily remembered for us. During the memorization of the word, connecting it to some household chores, doing it in practice, trying it becomes a natural acquisition for the child without difficulty. For example: ask your child to take a bowl to the table and ask him to count in English how many people there are in the house or count together. Say all the

equipment in the house in English. For example: if you want to say eat with a spoon, the main word is "spoon", if you say "eat with a spoon", the words in its dictionary will increase by one more.

The third effective method is to teach through everyday events.

In this method, everything around can be used. For example; yesterday you wore your "blue socks" and today you wear your "white socks". Or by naming his toys in English when you are cleaning his room with the child. For example: let's take your teddy bear upstairs, pack your things. Use of visible objects. For example: door [door], table [table], pen [pen].

The next method is teaching through books

Young children are interested in books with pictures and bright colors. You can ask what it is and what color it is, showing the thing depicted in the picture. For example: What color was the plane? What was in front of the dog?

The most interesting way for children is to teach a foreign language by showing cartoons.

It is even better if the cartoon is full of various songs with the participation of various animals. The child's ability to listen and understand improves. It is also easier to remember the names of animals. It follows that the child remembers at least 6 words from each cartoon. This means that if a child watches a cartoon for 30 minutes 3 days a week, the child's vocabulary will increase by 18 words in 1 week.

Reading a story or fairy tale is one of the tried and popular methods. Read the story in a suitable tone and voice. Talk to the child after the story is over. During the hearing, what did he pay more attention to, which words did he not understand and which ones did he remember. We remind you that the story should be composed of words that the child knows.

We know that children are curious and bored with sameness. Therefore, it is useful for them to teach using different news every time. If they are taught in the same way, they will remember the method and prepare. This stops them from striving.

There is probably no one who knows what your child likes better than you. Encouraging them for every success in language learning is another effective way to increase interest.

What topics should be taught to children first?

- numbers; - toys; - clothes;
- animals;
- body parts;

- colors;
- foods.

As your child's vocabulary increases, you will make the words more complicated. The main thing is that you know how to attract your child's attention. We must remember that teaching should be based on the interest of the child. As we mentioned above, if you are interested in a book, you should teach it through a book, if you are interested in a cartoon, you should teach it through it.

In short, the advantage of independent education is that your child can learn more, and you know your child's weaknesses, likes and dislikes. This will help him learn faster. Your child will not be able to choose in kindergarten, the teacher will decide for him, which will kill his interest. It follows that do not be indifferent to your child.

References:

1. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2020). Technologies of developing the ecological culture of students in the process of learning a foreign languages in higher educational institutions. *Solid State Technology*, 63(1s), 1816-1825.
2. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. *Central asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(12), 37-43.
3. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. *Общество и инновации*, 2(10/S), 251-256.
4. Tadjibaeva, A., & Tashlanova, N. (2020). The collaborative approach in content and language learning. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (6 (60)), 31-34.
5. Mamatovich, Z. R., & Ergashevna, T. A. (2019). Blended learning in higher education using LMS Moodle. *Образовательный процесс*, (5 (16)), 5-9.
6. Ergashevna, T. A. (2020). Specific features of the language in the development of culture. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 82-84.
7. Mukhammad, K. K., & ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022, December). THE ESSENCE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES* (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 91-93).
8. ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3 (10), 126-128.
9. Sarvinoz, T., & Shodiya, I. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA KOGNITIV LINGVISTIKA SHAKLLANISH TARIXIGA DOIR. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 51-54.

10. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2023). The Issues Related to Studying of Language and thought in Cognitive Linguistics. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 271-273.
11. Toshpulatova, M., & Ilhomjonova, R. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY. *Engineering problems and innovations*.
12. Toshpulatova, M. I. (2022). The main features in teaching English for specific purposes. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(5), 207-214.
13. Ikromovna, T. M. (2022). USE OF FOLKTALES IN ENGLISH LESSONS. *POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL*, 88.
14. Parpiyeva, M., & Jurayeva, M. (2023). Problems of linguoculturological and neurolinguistic study of phonetic means. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 3(02), 49-59.
15. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & SultanovnaUsmanova, S. (2023). Neyrolingvistika sohasini organish tendensiyalari. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 2(1), 53-59.
16. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & Alisher o'g'li, M. M. (2023). Morphology and syntax and crosslinguistic findings in neurolinguistics. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 18(8), 156-159.
17. Dilshoda, R. (2022). THE STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 20(2), 36-40.
18. Raximjonova, D. (2022). INGLIZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA KOMPOZITSIYA USULIDA SO 'Z YASALISHI HODISASINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(4), 710-713.
19. Raximjonova, D. (2023). STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPUTER SOFTWARE TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *Farg 'ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali*, (1), 448-452.
20. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). The Cognitive Aspect of the Purpose of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 16, 88-94.
21. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). Language Education as A System: Structure, Functions and Main Components. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 14, 141-146.
22. Djurayevna, T. N. (2022). Semantic and structural features of the vocabulary of color designation in english, uzbek and russian languages. *Global Book Publishing Services*, 01-123.
23. Juraeva, Z. Q. (2017). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE. *Форум молодых ученых*, (5 (9)), 5-9.